

Harnessing the potential of data in clinical PACS with an open-source DICOM server

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Introduction

Picture Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS) used in clinical workflows are rich with data in the form of images as well as associated annotations, segmentations and finding reports by specialists in radiology, nuclear medicine or radiation oncology. From a research perspective, annotated images constitute the raw material for radiomic, machine learning and similar AI-based initiatives. It is not straightforward however to harness the potential of the tremendous amount of data collected in PACS on a daily basis. This paper presents the solution developed at our institution to harness the potential of data in clinical PACS without interfering with daily activities.

Materials & Methods

The Orthanc DICOM server (version 1.5.4) [1] was deployed on a Linux-based (CentOS 7) blade (HP ProLiant DL380p Gen8, 16GB RAM, dual Xeon E5-2630 v2) located in the server room of our institution. The DICOM server relies on a Postgresql (version 9.2) database through a dedicated plugin (version 3.1), and is configured to expose a web interface that can be used to perform queries and explore content (Orthanc use CivetWeb [2] as a standalone web server). The research DICOM server lives in a network topology enacting the principle of least privileges and a small number of machines are allowed to connect through dedicated ports. While connections to the local (hospital) PACS are possible, links to a Diagnostic Imaging Repository (DIR) federating images from multiple institutions are preferred to avoid filling the local image cache with potentially old and clinically non-relevant studies, thereby affecting retrieval times in a significant manner for clinical activities. Both the local PACS and DIR are Enterprise Imaging products by Agfa HealthCare.

A first use case consisted in manually retrieving images of specific patients for a radiomic project. Although the clinical PACS allows users to view images, exports are not permitted. Since physical access to images is required for any image processing task, Orthanc was used to query the regional DIR and retrieve (C-MOVE) images. Built-in functionalities in Orthanc were then used to anonymize and export images to a local filesystem in DICOM format.

A second use case consisted in periodically querying Orthanc for brachytherapy patients, for whom DICOM-RT instances are pushed by clinicians during or after procedures. The objective was to compute dosimetric indices from RTDOSE, RTPLAN, RTSTRUCT objects, and to feed a research database with the results. The REST API of Orthanc was used for query/retrieve operations through Python scripts, which were also used for Dose Volume Histogram (DVH) calculations. Figure 2 illustrates the evolution of this data pipeline over time.

Figure 1: Evolution of data extraction pipelines over time, with Orthanc as part of the current solution.

A third use case, developed for a research project, consisted in using Orthanc to query the regional DIR for PET studies, and to parse associated Structured Reports for specific terms (through regular expressions). Hits were gathered in an encrypted PDF report highlighting matched terms along with associated StudyInstanceUID, StudyDate and PatientID. A Python script relying heavily on Orthanc's REST API was used to perform these operations in a few lines of code. Only lightweight SR instances were transferred between the DIR and Orthanc, and these instances were deleted from Orthanc afterwards.

Results

All use cases demonstrated the flexibility of Orthanc and its capacity to perform complex operations through its REST API, notably with Python scripting. These use cases are now used routinely at our institution for research purposes and have a null impact on clinical activities. They allow researchers to conduct radiomic and other image-based initiatives in an efficient and elegant manner. Orthanc, for instance, provides a framework to embed annotations and other expensive pieces of information in a standard format (DICOM), ensuring compliance with the FAIR data principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability)[3].

Discussion & Conclusions

The open-source Orthanc project is an essential element of our imaging research ecosystem. Its REST API allows researchers to use the programming language of their choice for image-based projects. Our experience shows that relying on such a DICOM-compliant software enforces good practices and fosters standard awareness, with benefits in term of interoperability and long-term reusability of data in accordance with the FAIR data principles [3].

References

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